

Train Intellectually Disabled – Life Skills and Give Them A Life: A Case Study

Vaheeda Kayikkara

Research Scholar, Mahatma Gandhi University,
Kottayam, Kerala, India

Training in life skills is one of the important interventions for people with intellectual disability. Life skills include personal skills such as eating, dressing and bathing, shopping, banking, phone use and housekeeping, social skills such as interacting with other people, playing with peers etc and vocational skills. Being independent in these skills enables a person to live independently.

There are various methods for training people with intellectual disability the various skills needed in daily living. Let us discuss some of them with as case study of a successful disabled student.

Task analysis the analysis of how a task is accomplished, including a detailed description of both manual and mental activities, task and element durations, task frequency, task allocation, task complexity, environmental conditions, necessary clothing and equipment, and any other unique factors involved in or required for one or more people to perform a given task.

Chaining is an instructional procedure used in behavioral psychology, experimental analysis of behavior and applied behavior analysis. It involves reinforcing individual responses occurring in a sequence to form a complex behavior.

Role play is the changing of one's behavior to assume a role, either unconsciously to fill a social role, or consciously to act out an adopted role. It helps the person gain confidence to handle the same situations in real life.

Many studies have shown that life skills **training in real life situations** is the most effective. This is also

because people with intellectual difficulties may struggle with generalization. In this method, the client is taken to a real life situation, like the shopping mall, or the post office where he is asked to do a task. The therapist or trainer goes with the client and prompts him whenever required. After a couple of times, the client may be confident to do the task without support.

Social stories are pictorial stories that depict life situations and people. They can be used to discuss various aspects of life skills, including the right way to respond in a situation. Social stories can be used to teach social skills, as well as skills related to ways to respond in an emergency situation and safe behaviors. Social stories can also be used to motivate a client to be independent.

Case study: Person with Intellectual disability earns income and confidence from Information Technology field

Twenty Two - year-old Unnikkuttan, a resident of Thiruvananthapuram district, Kerala State, an intellectually disabled, by birth. He born as a twin child but his twin brother died six days after his birth because of heart failure. His mother, the bravest and lovable person, in spite of death of his child, and Unnikkuttan's disability and sickness trained him to do all the personal, social skills with her love and care. She ways that she trained life skill to him using task analysis, chaining etc.. Now he has recovered much of his strength and became economically self-reliant and confident about the future.

When he was eight, he joined in a normal school run by state government as an inclusive education student. His colleagues gave strength and support and his

teachers inspired, trained, guided, cared, and loved him. The headmaster as well as the teacher gave him special care and they arranged every possible things which will help to increase Unnikuttan's ability, talent etc. He passed out from the school with distinction in Tenth Standard. And he shown his talent in Higher secondary level also by having first class marks.

After passing higher secondary level he joined in a government ITI, a little away from his home. His mother and brother guided and shown him how to get into a bus, take ticket, get down to the apt place etc. He shown his talent in ITI examination also

Now Unnikutan after working in two other places works in Techno park, as a computer expert. Unnikuttan learnt about money management from his parents and is now proud to manage his bank account by himself He is confident he can become physically stronger and also develop his intellectual capabilities to be successful in life.

